

ADVANTAGES AND DIFFICULTIES OF SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION

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Annotation: *Translation is the conversion of a message in the source language into a message in the target language. By definition, an accurate translation is impossible because different languages differ both in grammatical structure and in the simple number of words, not to mention the difference in cultures, which can also have an impact on the methods and results of translation.*

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What makes this complex activity possible? Usually we talk about a combination of certain abilities, knowledge and skills: fluency in languages, erudition, good reaction, the ability to quickly "reach" a more or less acceptable option in difficult situations - in general, all this is no different from what any interpreter should have. However, the possibility of simultaneous translation, when in many cases the translator does not know how to end the phrase, the beginning of which translates, must be provided by some mechanism.

Satisfactory simultaneous interpretation becomes possible when it is possible to assume with a sufficient degree of probability "where the speaker is going".

So, simultaneous translation is also largely possible due to what is called probabilistic forecasting, which is the basis of many types of human activity. In order for simultaneous translation to be more likely, it is necessary, first of all, to have a good idea of the topic (subject) that is being discussed at this conference, seminar or round table.

Let's focus on one more advantage of simultaneous translation. For the simultaneous interpreter to work effectively, it was necessary to isolate him from the noise of the meeting room, and make his speech accessible to every recipient (listener). At the same time, a radio variant for simultaneous interpretation was also created abroad.

Simultaneous interpretation quickly became "comfortable" for both speakers and translators. Speakers, because he expelled the interpreter from the rostrum, who often emphasized the speaker's illiteracy and tongue-tied speech with his professionalism, pushing him to the background and hurting his self-esteem. Translators, because their seclusion and verbal juggling of two languages gave them an aura of exclusivity and gave them a certain independence.

It is impossible not to add to the above what is really difficult that exists in the profession of simultaneous interpreter. First, the work of an interpreter in synchronous mode requires constant mobilization of attention and continuous speaking. This leads to the fact that after 20-30 minutes of translation, the synchronist becomes tired of the articular apparatus, the language becomes "cotton wool", self-control decreases, and serious errors occur in the translation text. It is for this reason that the mode of operation of simultaneous interpreters involves at least a forty-minute rest after twenty minutes of work, and, consequently, the creation of groups or teams of 3-4 people for each booth.

The second difficulty of simultaneous translation is related to the translator's reaction, or rather, his reactivity. The synchronist is forced to react instantly every second to words perceived by ear, or rather, phrases. That is why simultaneous translation deters slow people, although they have excellent command of a foreign language. A good knowledge of two or more languages is not a prerequisite for success as a simultaneous interpreter. The listed difficulties of simultaneous translation are redeemed by its invisible advantage. To work as a simultaneous interpreter, it is not necessary to have a perfect command of the usual set of conversational standards of a foreign language. And if pronunciation can be

worked out in the most boring phonetic exercises if desired, then remembering and correctly using the gender of nouns, conjugation of irregular verbs, and most importantly - an endless number of exceptions to the rules, for a person even with an outstanding memory in conditions of isolation from the corresponding language environment, is an extremely difficult task.

So, let's sum up the results from the perspective of generally accepted provisions on simultaneous translation. Simultaneous interpretation is indeed carried out simultaneously with the speaker's speech, which gives a significant gain in time and banishes from the conference rooms minutes and hours of endless languor that engulfed those present waiting for translations of a speech delivered in a language unknown to them. That is why simultaneous interpretation has become a mandatory attribute of major international conferences. Simultaneous interpretation requires a certain amount of endurance and appropriate training, which can develop speech reactivity in the interpreter. Simultaneous translation is easier and better when translating from your native language to a foreign language, and not vice versa, as many people believe. Given all this, it can be stated that the "choice" of a simultaneous interpreter is only in the appropriate professional training, which, as you know, is necessary for any specialist.

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